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VMS mineral system characterization and deposit model

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Summary	Description of volcanogenic massive sulfide (VMS) deposits mineral system and deposit model for Outokumpu-type deposits
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1. Introduction

1.1. DeepBEAT Task 2.1

The objective of the task is to provide information of the Saramäki volcanogenic massive sulfide (VMS) deposit, encompassing exploration and research data of previous campaigns. The data were summarized and digitized, including existing drill core geochemical, mineralogical and petrophysical data, geological maps, reprocessed geophysical data, such as regional to local (target) geophysics (magnetic, electromagnetic), gravity data, and surficial geochemistry. These data are integrated into a deposit model employing a mineral system approach for ultramafic-hosted VMS deposit, which will be used for 3D mineral prospectivity modelling.

2. Volcanogenic Massive Sulfide (VMS) deposits

Volcanogenic massive sulfide deposits form at or near the seafloor in submarine volcanic environments, typically in rift environments such as at mid-ocean ridges e.g., Mid-Atlantic Ridge, or volcanic arc settings, either at back-arc spreading centers or forearc spreading centers. These rift zones enable upwelling of mafic magmas and drive high-temperature hydrothermal circulation and induce crustal melting, forming felsic magmas. According to the USGS VMS database 1090 VMS deposits are known worldwide (Mosier et al. 2009). They range in age from 3.4 Ga in the Archean Pilbara craton of Australia to Miocene age (15 Ma) deposits in Japan (Galley et al. 2007). Seafloor massive sulfide deposits (SMS) are also currently forming at modern seafloor with over 300 known sulfide occurrences (Petersen et al. 2018). VMS deposits are major sources of Zn, Cu, Pb, Ag, and Au, and significant sources for Co, Sn, Se, Mn, Cd, In, Bi, Te, Ga, and Ge. A number of these elements are classified as critical or strategic in EU (European Commission 2025). The median size of VMS deposits is generally 1–3 Mt with typical grades of a few percent of Cu and Zn, minor to moderate Pb (<1 %), 5–50 g/t Ag and 0.2–2 g/t Au. The biggest deposits in Finland reach 20–75 Mt including e.g., Vihanti 28 Mt, Outokumpu 28.5 Mt and Pyhäsalmi 75 Mt (GTK 2025). Several are also located at the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB) of southern Spain and Portugal reach giant to supergiant size classes with > 100 Mt of ore.

In the past, VMS deposits have been classified based on the dominant metal(s), e.g., Cu, Cu-Zn, and Zn-Pb-Cu types, or based on type locations: Cyprus-type for Cu-rich deposits hosted by mafic volcanics in ophiolites, Kuroko-type for Cu-Zn deposits hosted by felsic volcanics and Besshi-type for Cu-Zn deposits hosted by mafic volcanics and pelitic metasediments. Currently, the deposits are classified based on their host rocks into 5 main types: Mafic, siliciclastic-mafic, bimodal-mafic, bimodal-felsic and siliciclastic-felsic, which also reflect their lithotectonic settings, e.g., mid-ocean ridges, back-arcs, intra-oceanic arcs or continental margin arcs (Franklin et al. 2005) (Fig. 1). More recently Patten et al. (2022) proposed a new class of VMS deposit hosted with ultramafic rocks in ophiolites, which often contain economic concentrations of Co and sometimes also Ni, in addition to Cu and Zn.

Figure 1. Schematic tectonic settings for seafloor VMS deposits and examples of modern locations (modified after Schultz 2010).

Figure 2. Generalized cross section of oceanic crust at extensional setting (e.g., mid-ocean ridge) and components of high-temperature hydrothermal system.

Figure 2 shows a generalized cross-section of oceanic crust at an extensional setting, such as a mid-ocean ridge, where cold seawater is drawn downwards into the crust. As the temperature of the seawater increases it leaches metals and sulfur from the rocks. The resultant high-temperature (typically 350°C) fluid flow upwards along a focused up-flow zone and finally exits to seafloor, or subseafloor within loose sediments or volcanoclastic deposits, mixes with cold seawater and precipitates metals as sulfides. Depending on the fluid salinity and temperature the sulfides form mounds or more stratiform deposits. More saline fluids can also form brine pools such as the Atlantis II Deep at the Red Sea (containing 90 Mt, Guney et al. 1988) (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Styles of sulfide deposition at or below seafloor (modified after Tornos et al. 2015).

VMS deposits typically occur as massive to semi-massive sulfides (25 to >50 % sulfides) and also as breccia-types, veins and disseminations. The most common sulfide minerals are pyrite, pyrrhotite, chalcopyrite, sphalerite and galena and the most common gangue (non-ore minerals) include quartz, carbonate, barite, muscovite and chlorite.

VMS deposits are often underlain by an alteration zone (e.g., Fig. 3), which can show zoning from inner high-T zone of intense silica alteration with sulfide veins, followed by chlorite-rich alteration zone, sericite zone and an outer zone of weak Si-Na metasomatism. Ultramafic host rock show ubiquitous sea floor serpentinization and high-temperature Mg-Ca-Si metasomatism (talc-carbonate alteration).

2.1. Mineral system model for VMS deposits

Mineral system models help to understand the geological processes that form ore deposits and also preserve them. The formation of an ore deposit is a small, localized expression of larger geological processes that operate at variable scales, focusing energy and material fluxes (McCuaig et al. 2010). Mineral system models can be used in exploration targeting or mineral

prospectivity modeling/analysis by translating the various parts of the mineral system into mappable criteria from which, spatial proxies can be identified (Fig. 1).

Mineral system model can be divided into components or processes, which cover the whole mineralizing process from the energy driving the system to the transport of ore forming elements and finally the actual ore formation. The commonly used components are described below:

1. Energy to drive the mineralization process, i.e. to form a magma or a hydrothermal system.
2. Ligands or complexing agents to transport the metals. In hydrothermal systems these are typically chlorine ions and/or reduced sulfur species.
3. A source of metals. This can be magma, or in a hydrothermal system, suitable upper crustal rocks. In most cases this does not require any pre-concentration processes at the source.
4. Transport pathways for magma or fluid from the source to the site of deposition, represented by fault and fracture zones in hydrothermal systems.
5. Physical and/or chemical barriers (traps) for ore deposition. In hydrothermal systems this can happen by e.g. fluid interaction with reactive rock formation or mixing with seawater.
6. Finally, the process of ore formation can leave footprints such as alteration zones or dispersions of ore constituents, or the spent fluids can form distinct distal rock formations.

Generalized mineral system model for VMS deposits

Modified after Knox-Robinson and Wyborn, 1997

Figure 4. Generalized mineral system model for VMS deposits and associated mappable criteria and spatial proxies.

Figure 4 shows a generalized mineral system model for VMS deposits and associated mappable criteria and spatial proxies. In VMS systems energy and also in some cases metals are provided by sub-seafloor magma chamber, downward penetrating seawater provides ligands in the form of Cl^- ions and acts as the transport medium of metals. As the temperature of the water increases it reacts with the surrounding rocks and lowers to pH of the fluid, which enables leaching of various metals and sulfur from the oceanic crust. The fluid becomes also more reducing and converts seawater sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) to sulfidic sulfur (H_2S), which also acts as a complexing agent. Syn-volcanic faults act as fluid pathways/conduits. Metals are precipitated below or on the seafloor as the hydrothermal fluid mixes with cold seawater.

2.2. Ultramafic-hosted VMS deposits

Compared to the mafic to felsic hosted deposits, ultramafic-hosted deposits are less common either in ancient on-land settings or on the modern seafloor. However, based on more recent studies on modern seafloor sulfide occurrences, Fouquet et al. (2014) proposed a new class of ultramafic-hosted seafloor massive sulfide deposits (UM-SMS), which has been expanded to on land deposits by Patten et al. (2022). Modern UM-SMS deposits are found on slow to ultra-slow spreading MOR environments, such as parts of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge and SW- and Central Indian Ridge, closely associated with low-angle detachment faults (Fig. 5). They are usually Cu-rich (1.5–20 %), with variable Zn grades (0.1–25 %) and often with elevated to high Co contents from hundreds of ppm up to 0.5 % but low on Pb (<100–400 ppm). Nickel contents are generally lower but can reach about 0.1 % (Fouquet et al. 2010). However, it should be noted that the metal concentrations represent relatively low number of grab samples and actual average concentration are probably much lower. The deeply penetrating faults at slow spreading rate ocean ridges allow fluid reaction with ultramafic rocks, producing H_2 and CH_4 resulting in more reducing conditions and a reduced sulfide assemblage of pyrrhotite (instead of pyrite), isocubanite and relatively Fe-rich sphalerite (Charlou et al. 2010, Patten et al 2022).

Ancient, ultramafic-hosted (or mixed mafic-ultramafic) on land VMS deposits are almost ubiquitously associated with ophiolites, i.e., slices of oceanic crust obducted onto continental crust (Coleman 1971) in a convergent plate tectonic environment. As their modern counterparts, they are typically Cu dominant (1–6 %), with subordinate Zn (0.1–1.5 %) and low Pb (≤ 0.1 %). Typical Co grades vary from 0.07–0.08 % in mafic dominant deposits to 0.1–0.5 % in ultramafic dominant deposits. Nickel contents are often much lower (if known) but in some deposits, especially with more dominantly ultramafic host-rocks, Ni contents can reach 0.1–0.2 %. Global examples of mafic-ultramafic, ophiolite hosted deposits include Chu Chua, Soucy No 1 and Windy Craggy in Canada, Shomakawa in Japan, Deerni in China, Kure deposits in Turkey, Ishkinino, Ivanovka, Letneye, Sibayskoye (bimodal-felsic) and Dergamysh in Urals Russia, and Monte Bardeneto, Reppia and Corcia in northern Italy (Table 1).

Patten et al. (2022) proposed three possible tectonic settings for ultramafic-hosted VMS deposits associated with deep detachment faults: 1) Ocean-Continent Transition (OCT) zones, 2) slow to ultra-slow spreading rate mid-ocean ridges and 3) supra-subduction zones (SSZ) in fore-arc settings. OCTs represent magma-poor rifting of continental margins that develop into the

formation of oceanic crust. A good example of this type of transition zone is found offshore of Iberia, where a 160 km wide zone where the eastern part (near shore) represents unroofed continental mantle, whereas the oceanward end represents development of oceanic crust and increased magmatic activity (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Schematic representations of possible geotectonic locations for ultramafic-hosted VMS deposits, related to mantle exhumation via detachment faults (modified after Patten et al. 2022).

Figure 6. Schematic cross section of detachment fault and related hydrothermal system and mineralizations (modified after Patten et al. 2022).

At slow- to ultraslow-spreading mid-ocean ridges, extension can exceed magmatic activity and asymmetric spreading (extension is faster on one side of the ridge compared to the other) often

results in the formation of detachment fault that exhumes mantle rock to the seafloor (Fig. 6) and in the formation of ocean core complexes (OCC). The time frame for formation of an OCC and the activity of the detachment can be up to a few million years (e.g. Cannant et al. 2006; Escartin et al. 2007, Lang et al. 2025). Examples of modern slow- to ultraslow-spreading rate mid ocean ridges include several sections of the Mid-Atlantic ridge and South-West and Central Indian Ridges. The third setting is less common in modern seafloor with bets examples at Banda arc (Eastern Indonesia) and South Sandwich fore-arc (South Atlantic Ocean).

The above-described tectonic settings have several features that are favorable for the formation SMS/VMS deposits: The slow spreading rate and low magmatic budget promote long lived extension and generation of permeable crust through faulting and facilitating the development of deep penetrating detachment faults, reaching up to 13 km beneath seafloor (Escartin et al. 2008, Tao et al. 2020). Consequently, they can host long lived (up to 200–300 ky), high-temperature hydrothermal systems with reaction-zone fluid temperatures up to 450–500°C (Escartin et al. 2008, Tao et al. 2020, Jamieson et al. 2023; Yang et al. 2023). Fluid reaction with predominantly ultramafic rocks decreases fluid pH, which, together with high temperature, enhances metal leaching and solubility. The enrichment of Co and to lesser extent Ni in many modern and ancient ultramafic-mafic hosted VMS deposit is a combination of several factors, e.g. the presence of ultramafic rocks provide source for Ni and Co (much higher Ni and Co compared to mafic rocks), the low pH and high temperature of the fluid increase solubility of these elements and the tectonic setting is favorable for a long lived hydrothermal system.

Table 1. Examples of ultramafic-hosted (or mafic-ultramafic) VMS deposits in ancient ophiolites (Windy Craggy represent accreted arc terrane).

Deposit	Country	Type	Tonnage Mt	Cu %	Zn %	Pb %	Co %	Ni %
Chu Chua	Canada	Mafic	7	2	0.4	0	0.1	
Soucy No 1	Canada	Mafic silisiclastic	4.32	1.4	1.09	0.1	0.09	
Windy Graggy	Canada	Mafic silisiclastic	297	1.38	0.25		0.069	
Shimokawa	Japan	Mafic silisiclastic	8	2.28	1.34	0	0.13-0.27	
Deerni (Dur'ngoi)	China	Mafic-ultramafic	0.75	1.27	1.05		0.089	
Kure (Asikoy)	Turkey	Mafic-ultramafic	13.6	2.17	0.1	0.02	0.3	
Kure (Magaradoruk)	Turkey	Mafic-ultramafic	29	5.07	1.17	≤0.028	0.56	≤0.01
Ishkinino	Russia	Ultramafic	1	6.4	0.2	<0.002	0.2	0.3
Ivanovskoe (Ivanovka)	Russia	Mafic-ultramafic	10	1.08	0.3		0.4	0.1-0.2
Letneye	Russia	Mafic	6	2.8	1.2	0.05	0.17	
Sibaiskoye	Russia	Bimodal-felsic	100	1	1.56	0.04	0.13	
Dergamysh	Russia	Ultramafic	2	1.38	0.03-2	<0.002	0.01-0.25	0.01-0.35
Monte Bardeneto	Italy	Ultramafic	?	0.55-3.12	0.01-0.17	<0.001	0.053	0.059
Reppia I	Italy	Ultramafic	?	1.67-5	0.02-0.05		0.23	0.069
Corcia Fe-Cu	Italy	Mafic-ultramafic	?	0.98-5.98	0.039-0.27	<0.01	0.12-0.53	0.029-0.1
Corcia Cu	Italy	Mafic-ultramafic	?	5.9	0.08		0.35	0.32
Corcia-Zn	Italy	Mafic-ultramafic	?	0.13-0.58	11.5-32.3	<0.03	0.1-0.17	≤0.0016

Data from Mosier et al. (2009), Herrington et al. (2005), Peter and Scott (1993), Akbulut et al. (2016), Altun et al. (2015), Meleketseva et al. (2013), Nimis et al. (2008), Prokin and Buslaev (1999), Maslennikov et al. (2019), Zaccarini and Garuti (2008).

3. Geology of the Outokumpu region and the Outokumpu ophiolite

The Outokumpu region is located in eastern Finland, approximately 450 km north-east from the capital of Helsinki. Geologically, the area is dominated by Paleoproterozoic (ca. 2.1–1.9 Ga) metasediments, i.e., mica schists and mica gneisses representing the so-called Lower and Upper Kalevian sequences, forming the North Karelia Schist Belt. These are bound by Archean (3.0–2.7 Ga) granites and gneisses in the east and north and by Svekofennian (1.9–1.8 Ga) formations in the west. The Archean craton experienced prolonged rifting between 2.45–2.0 Ga culminating in a continental margin (passive margin – rifted margin) setting and probably generation of oceanic crust in parts of the belt as evidenced by the ca.1.95 Ga Jormua ophiolite and fragments of the Outokumpu ophiolite (e.g. Peltonen et al. 2008, Lahtinen et al. 2010). The older (maximum age 2.1 to 2.0 Ga), Lower Kalevian metasediments were deposited at shallow to deep water setting possible in a deepening rift or passive margin basin, whereas the more monotonous

Figure 7. Geological map of the Outokumpu region and location of Outokumpu-type Cu-Zn-Co-Ni deposits and Ni-Co-Cu deposits (Saramäki deposit and Miihkali massif indicated).

Upper Kaleva metasediments (greywackes (mica schists) with minor graphitic muds (black schists)) were deposited at deeper water conditions on continental slope-rise and possibly on seafloor (oceanic crust) at more distal parts with a maximum depositional age of 1.95 to 1.92

Ga. Fragments of the Outokumpu ophiolite are all found within the Upper Kalevian metasediments. Early stages of the Svecofennian orogen (collision between the Archean craton and Paleoproterozoic microcontinent – volcanic arc collage) resulted in thrust sheets of Upper Kalevian metasediments and ophiolite fragments, and also between the metasediments and ophiolite fragments. Finally, the metasediment formations were deformed during the peak of the Svecofennian orogen at ca. 1.88 Ga.

3.1. Outokumpu ophiolite and associated polymetallic VMS deposits

The ca. 1.96 Ga Outokumpu ophiolite represents a highly dismembered and fragmented ophiolite, mostly composed of residual mantle peridotites (ultramafics) with smaller proportions of mafic intrusive bodies (including dyke-in-dyke textures indicating extensional environment) and volcanic rocks, and the closely associated black schists occurring together in the lower parts of the Upper Kaleva mica schists. All the ultramafic-mafic lithologies have been altered to serpentinites after peridotites and amphibole and chlorite replacing original magmatic minerals in the mafic rock types. The size of the ophiolite blocks range in size from just a few meters up to 20 km in length, the largest bodies represented by the Outokumpu-Vuonos zone and the Saramäki-Miihkali massif in the NE part of the North Karelia Schist Belt (Fig. 7). A typical feature of this Outokumpu rock package or assemblage is the interfingering with the surrounding mica schists along thrust faults and due to complex folding. Serpentinites in the immediate wall rocks of the sulfide mineralizations show zonal alteration from inner quartz(\pm tremolite \pm carbonate)-rock, tremolite \pm diopside \pm carbonate skarns (calc-silicate rock) and carbonate rocks as the most distal type. The total thickness of this alteration envelope varies from ca. 10 to 50 meters. The contacts between different types of alteration zones can be gradational or sharp and they can also vary from one type to another at meter scale. The relatively high Cr and Ni contents (typically 0.1–0.3 %) indicate that they all originate from the serpentinite protolith (Peltonen et al. 2008, Huhma et al. 2018).

There are 11 known Outokumpu-type polymetallic VMS deposits in the Outokumpu region, ranging in size from the sizeable Outokumpu deposit (28 Mt), which was mined from 1910 to 1989, to the small Sola deposit (Table 2). In addition to the Outokumpu deposit, three of the other, multimillion ton deposits have been mined. Typically, mineralization occurs as sheets, lenses or ruler-shaped bodies of semimassive to massive sulfides, while some show more complex geometries due to deformation and faulting. The main sulfide minerals are pyrite (FeS_2) and/or pyrrhotite (Fe_{1-x}S), chalcopyrite (CuFeS_2) and sphalerite ($(\text{ZnFe})\text{S}$). Cobalt and Ni are mostly hosted in cobaltpentlandite ($(\text{Co,Ni,Fe})_9\text{S}_8$), although in some deposits pyrite and pyrrhotite contain also significant percentage of Co (although the contents are low in the sulfide phases). Quartz is the main non-ore mineral, together with lesser amounts of tremolite and carbonate.

Table 2. Grade-tonnage data for Outokumpu type Cu-Zn-Co-Ni deposits.

Deposit	Cu wt. %	Zn wt. %	Co wt. %	Ni wt. %	Aug/t	Ag g/t	Tonnage Mt
Outokumpu*	3.8	1.07	0.24	0.12	0.8	8.9	28.5
Kylylahti*	1.25	0.54	0.24	0.2	0.6	3.5	8.4
Luikonlahti*	1.2	0.65	0.12	0.09			7.7
Vuonos*	2.3	1.6	0.15	0.13	0.1	11	6.2
Saramäki	0.71	0.63	0.09	0.05			3.4
Perttilahti	2.15	1.89	0.16	0.15		14	1.3
Riihilahti	0.72	0.09	0.09	0.03	0.3	6	0.7
Kettukumpu	0.44	0.1	0.07	0.18			0.4
Hietajärvi	0.67	1.13	0.14	0.18			0.34
Hoikka	0.5	0.1	0.04	0.15			0.2
Sola	2	1	0.1	0.15			0.1

*Past producing mine

3.1.1. Saramäki deposit

The Saramäki deposit is located in the northern part of the Outokumpu region (Fig. 7). It forms the southernmost part of the so called Miihkali serpentinite batholith (immediately north of Saramäki in Fig. 7), which is one of the most sizeable ophiolite fragments in the region, extending some 15 km north-south, with a maximum width of 1.6 km and vertical extend of 500 to 700 meters. The core of the massif is composed of altered ultramafic rocks (metaperidotites, serpentinites, talc-carbonate rocks) with minor metagabbros and chlorite schists while the more peripheral parts are very heterogeneous with varying amounts of skarns rocks, metabasites and quartz rocks and black schists at the contact zones. Although the Miihkali massif contains similar alteration as the Outokumpu deposits, no mineralization are known from the massif.

In the southern part of the massif, where the Saramäki deposit is located, Outokumpu-type rocks occur as in two areas, here termed as Saramäki North and Saramäki South, separated by faulting and deformation, although the extent of the Outokumpu assemblage is probably more extensive and continue further south and east, at least at depth, than the current geological (surface bedrock) map indicates. Based on the fairly extensive drillings in the area (see section 3.2), the northern part forms a relatively thin (150 m), flat-lying slab of serpentinites and talc-carbonate rocks (ultramafics), skarns, metabasites, quartz-rock and associated black schists. Towards east, the rock package dip turns near vertical and then again near horizontal at depth in the westernmost drill hole. In some drill profiles, the upper horizon is underlain by two ad-

ditional 5–50 m intervals of Outokumpu rocks with mica schist intercalations. Sulfide mineralization is only encountered in a few drill holes in the Saramäki N area, probably indicating the presence of small lenses of mineralized rock.

In the southern Saramäki area, the Outokumpu rock package forms a 40–80 m thick slab dipping at 20–25° angle to east (Fig. 8). The lithology of this slab is quite variable and heterogeneous, but the dominant rock types are tremolite skarns and other skarn rocks with subordinate ultramafics, chlorite schists, quartz rocks and carbonate rocks. Black schist occur generally throughout the sequence. Typical features are the high variability of rock types over relatively short drill intervals, mineralogical variability of rock types e.g. tremolite skarns of the contain variable amounts of chlorite, biotite, carbonate, talc, and quartz although more massive and representative intervals of “pure” rock types also occur, banded textures that could indicate replacement of mica schist (rather than an ultramafic protolith). In the following, we provide short descriptions of the main rock types at Saramäki.

Figure 8. Simplified cross section of the Saramäki deposit showing Outokumpu assemblage rocks, mineralization and drill holes (modified after Kontinen et al. 2006).

Skarns

In the strict sense of the term, skarn rocks are formed through alteration of original carbonate-containing protolith and typically are made of garnet and pyroxene as main minerals. Here the term is used for altered rocks, regardless of protolith, that are typically composed of tremolite (tremolite skarn), in some cases actinolite (skarn) with or without diopsidic pyroxene (tremolite-diopside skarn). Skarns are by far the most common rock type at Saramäki. They can occur as up to 10 m intervals of near monomineralic tremolite skarns, but more typically they occur intermixed with other rock types (Fig. 9) and are mineralogically more heterogeneous containing, in addition to tremolite, variable amounts of chlorite, biotite, carbonate and quartz. Based on visual inspection of drill core, in some cases the skarns seem to overprint/replace mica schists. However, the available whole-rock analytical data indicates fairly mafic-to ultramafic

protolith based on the relatively high, though variable, MgO contents (~10–30 wt.% MgO, median 12.8 wt.%) and high Cr contents (200–4000 ppm, median ~1000 ppm). Chromium as an immobile element can be considered as a more reliable indicator than MgO.

Figure 9. Light grey tremolite skarn with pale green chlorite schist interval. Drill hole PVJ/SAR-12.

Serpentinite and talc-carbonate rocks (ultramafic rocks)

Altered ultramafic rocks also form a mineralogically diverse group. They are composed of variable amounts serpentine, talc, carbonate, chlorite and tremolite, varying from relatively pure serpentinite and talc-carbonate rocks (soap stone) to talc-chlorite-tremolite schists, etc. As mentioned earlier these ultramafic rock types are more common in the northern Saramäki area and less voluminous in the southern Saramäki area. Geochemically they are more consistently ultramafic with over 20 wt. % MgO (often $\geq 30\%$ MgO) and over 2000 ppm Cr.

Chlorite schists

Chlorite schists occur as 2–10 m intervals of massive chlorite schist/rock or as more heterogeneous intervals, containing variable amounts of tremolite, biotite, carbonate or talc. Like the skarn rocks, chlorite schists tend to be quite mafic to ultramafic in composition with very similar median contents of MgO (12.9 wt. %, often ≥ 20 wt. %) and Cr (~1000 ppm, often >1000 ppm). In the Miihkali massif area, chlorite schists occur commonly as narrow intervals within serpentinites, probably as alteration products of mafic dykes and possibly volcanic rocks.

Quartz rock

Quartz rocks are less common and form a highly heterogeneous group with variable mineralogical and chemical composition. Quartz rock intervals tend to be quite short, typically only 0.5 to 2 m in length. Typical impurities include tremolite-actinolite, mica and carbonate. Geochemically, they contain highly variable SiO₂ contents, very rarely they even approach “pure” quartz rock compositions (>90 wt. % SiO₂). The high Cr contents indicate ultramafic origin. However, there is also a low Cr (100–300 ppm) quartz rock type, which is often at least moderately sulfide mineralized, possibly pointing to different formation processes.

Carbonate rock

Carbonate rocks are even less frequent than quartz rocks. They typically occur as 1-3 m intervals intermixed with other rock types and contain variable amounts of tremolite and chlorite. Calcite

and dolomite are the main carbonate minerals with high CaO and moderate MgO contents. High Cr contents indicate ultramafic protolith for the carbonate rocks, but overall low Cr concentrations indicate other types of protoliths as well, or direct precipitation of carbonate minerals at or below seafloor.

Metabasite

Metabasite is a general term for a mafic rock type with ambiguous protolith. In many cases this could be a mafic vulcanite or a dyke rock, based on the moderate MgO and Cr contents (~10 wt.% MgO and 300–600 ppm Cr). Some types contain relatively high MgO and Cr, i.e., ≥ 20 wt.% MgO, >1000 ppm Cr, resembling skarns and chlorite schists and original logging indicate appreciable amounts of chlorite, indicating more ultramafic protolith.

Black schists

Narrow intervals of black schists occur within the mica schists, but more significant black schists are intimately associated with the Outokumpu assemblage at Saramäki, and other Outokumpu type deposits. Black schists can occur throughout the whole package, often in the immediate footfall but also within the sequence. As with the other rock types, typical intersection varies from 1 to 3 meters, locally reaching up to 10 meters. Typical S and graphitic carbon contents are 1–5 wt.% with slightly elevated base metals, generally 0.1 to 0.2 wt.% Zn, in close proximity to sulfide mineralization they can also contain elevated Cu (0.1–0.2 wt.%).

Sulfide mineralization

The sulfide mineralization at Saramäki occurs as a 1 to 10 m thick zone of mostly semi-massive sulfides with a halo of low-grade disseminated sulfides. Mineralization tends to occur at the lower portion of the host-rock package, with tremolite skarns, quartz rock and chlorites schists (Fig. 10). The known mineralization occurs as a 200–300 m wide sheet, dipping from the surface to a depth of ca. 220 m towards east at an angle of 20–25 degrees. The exact extent of the mineralization towards east is unknown, although limited drilling by Boliden indicates the presence of Outokumpu rocks ca. 700 m east of mineralization outcrop but with only weak sulfide mineralization with 0.16–0.18 wt.% Cu. More sparse drillings towards north – north-west of the main Saramäki mineralization indicates that the mineralization turns and dips towards NW as a narrower ruler-like body to the vertical depth of ca. 675 meters, extending for strike length of ca. 1 km. The grade tonnage data for Saramäki determined by Outokumpu Oy in the 1980's is shown in Table 2. Compared to the mined deposits, average grades are lower, however massive-semimassive sulfide intercepts can reach 1–3 wt.% combined Cu, Zn, Co and Ni (e.g. Fig. 10 core box).

Figure 10. Massive to patchy semimassive sulfides (bronze and yellow) with quartz rock (light grey) and greenish tremolite-(chlorite) skarn and chlorite schist in drill hole PVJ/SAR-12. Between 73.30 and 76.92 meters Cu varies from 1.3 to 2.94 wt. %, Zn from 0.1 to 0.26 wt. %, Co from 0.07 to 0.22 wt. % and Ni from 0.05 to 0.15 wt. %.

Of the minor elements typically enriched in VMS deposits (As, Bi, Sb, Se, Sn, Te) only Sn is more or less systematically present in Outokumpu type deposits, elevated Sn has also been reported from other ultramafic-hosted deposits, although it should be noted that there are only a very limited number of analyses available of these elements (Table 3). Arsenic concentrations can reach several hundreds of ppm's but high concentrations tend to be sporadic. Selenium is elevated in massive sulfides (tens of ppm's) but generally relatively low at Saramäki, possibly again due to low number of analyses, especially of Cu-rich massive sulfides. Antimony, Bi and Te concentrations are generally a few ppm's at maximum, some Zn-rich massive sulfides are more enriched in Sb.

Table 3. Whole rock and selected trace-element contents in the Saramäki deposit (after Peltonen et al. 2008). Drill hole locations in Figure 11.

Drill core	JU/MI-29	JU/MI-38	JU/MI-53	JU/MI-103	JU/MI-103	JU/MI-103
Depth (m)	494.3–495.5	122.35–123.45	363–364.12	136.6–136.8	142.6–142.65	143.6–144.1
SiO ₂ (wt. %)	n.a.	63.9	56.9	42.3	31.6	86.6
TiO ₂	n.a.	0.096	<0.005	0.131	0.023	<0.005
Al ₂ O ₃	n.a.	1.88	0.05	2.8	0.53	0.09
Fe ₂ O ₃	n.a.	21.2	32.5	14.3	34.7	8.46
MnO	n.a.	0.026	0.021	0.144	0.074	0.009
CaO	n.a.	1.75	1.13	15.5	5.59	0.19
Na ₂ O	n.a.	0.52	<0.07	0.34	0.1	<0.07
K ₂ O	n.a.	0.256	<0.004	0.057	0.023	<0.04
P ₂ O ₅	n.a.	0.021	<0.015	0.055	0.294	<0.015
S	28.3	11.3	16.7	6.04	17.3	4.61
C	1.62	1.02	0.38	3.11	1.86	0.11
Cu (ppm)	13400	9840	10100	1580	5430	2760
Zn	12500	591	815	272	16100	116
Co	1640	264	619	85	681	193

Ni	838	456	664	352	615	132
Pb	2.9	5.33	2.49	1.52	3.62	2.24
Ag	6.1	5.3	6.1	0.9	2.3	1.5
Cd	18	1.5	2.3	0.3	19	<0.1
Sn	7.72	1	<1	2	7	<1
Sb	<0.1	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.1
Se	1.1	0.3	0.3	1	5.2	2.1
As	7	4	579	1.2	<1	4
Bi	0.09	0.07	<0.05	0.18	<0.05	0.07
Te	0.25	<0.05	<0.05	0.077	<0.01	<0.01
Cr	10	38	<30	58	<30	<30
V	23.4	80.8	28	241	39	4.48
Sulfides	Massive	Disseminated	Semi-massive	Disseminated	Semi-massive	Disseminated
Gangue	Qz-tre-di	Qz	Qz	Tre-di	Qz-tre-di	Qz

3.2. Exploration data

The Saramäki area has been active prospected by different exploration companies in several phases over the years. Outokumpu Oy started exploration in the area, based on the occurrence of Outokumpu assemblage rocks in the late 1960's and again from late 1970's to early 1980's. Outokumpu drilled the Miihkali massive, and especially in the Saramäki area, fairly extensively (75 drill holes for a total length of 31,929 m). The drilling data was collected and combined in the joint GTK-Outokumpu GEOMEX project in late 1990's into an MS Access database containing the drill whole collar locations, geological and analytical data. However, this data does not include original, detailed drill core logs, some of which might be found in original Outokumpu reports but only a few (if any) of these have been digitized. In addition, Outokumpu conducted several campaigns of ground geophysics (magnetic and electromagnetic methods), again covering the whole Saramäki-Miihkali area. Details of geophysics and petrophysics are described in the following section 3.2. The whole area was also covered with till sampling (lines), however this data is only available as a report and the original data is not available in numeric format. A few short till sampling lines and more dense soil line sampling was conducted at Saramäki (and Miihkali massif).

Kylylahti Copper (Altona Mining) drilled 11 holes totaling 1379 m (PVJ/SAR in Figure 11) between 2006 and 2008; 5 in the Saramäki N and 6 in the known mineralization area. In addition, mobile metal ion (MMI) sampling was conducted along two 1km long lines; one crossing the outcropping mineralization and one 0.6 km to the north.

Figure 11. Generalized geological map from Saramäki area with mica schist in blue and Outokumpu rocks in brown. Also indicated are Outokumpu Oy, Boliden and Kylylahti Copper drillings. Drill holes in red indicate the presence of sulfide mineralization.

The most recent exploration was conducted by the Swedish Boliden corporation, encompassing the whole Miihkali-Saramäki area. In the Saramäki area, these include ground magnetic and electromagnetic surveys, surface till sampling, Ionic leach of soil samples, and drilling in more peripheral parts of the area. The surface till sampling (160 samples) was done by hand and represents rather wide spaced sampling. Samples were analyzed by hand-held XRF (pXRF) from sieved fraction (<2 mm) and checked against limited number of laboratory analyses. Due to the relatively high detection limits of pXRF, Co is below detection limits in all sample locations, 80 % of Ni analyses are below d.l., 50 % for Cu, whereas Zn is above detection limit in almost every sampling point, indicating limited usefulness for pXRF method. Boliden also analyzed soil samples by Ionic leach from two diagonal till sampling lines, unfortunately the sampling locations and analytical data cannot be combined as sample labels lack analysis labels (and vice versa). One short till sampling line was done parallel to Outokumpu sampling line across the subcropping mineralization (see Fig. 12 for sampling point locations).

The Geological Survey of Finland (GTK) has not done any targeted exploration in the Saramäki area, however as a national geosurvey GTK has done extensive country-wide surveys including low-altitude aerogeophysics (magnetic, electromagnetic and radiometric), generally by 1:100 000 map sheets. The Saramäki-Miihkali area was flown in 1980. GTK

Figure 12. Index maps showing the location of Outokumpu till and soil sampling (left) and Boliden and Kylylahti Copper till and MMI sampling points on the right.

Table 4. List of exploration data by various exploration/mining companies.

Outokumpu Oy data				
Drillings	Total m	AAS analyses	XRF (me*)	XRF+ICP-MS**
75 ddh	31929	3880 (base metals)	739	30
Till	2 lines, 66 points	Cu, Zn, Ni, Co by AAS, aqua regia (?) digestion		
Soil	10 lines, 139 points	Ashed samples, Cu, Zn, Ni, Co, Pb, Mn by AAS, nitric acid digestion		
Ground geophysics	Coverage			
Magnetic	Extensive	50 m line spacing, 5–20 m station spacing		
EM	Extensive	50 m line spacing, 20 m station spacing		
Gravity	Extensive	100–500 m line spacing, 20 m station spacing		
Boliden data				
Drillings	Total m	ICP-AES, fire assay AAS for Au	ICP-MS, fire assay for Au	
7 ddh	3383	35 elements+Au	48 elements+Au	
Till	160 +30	pXRF (160 samples) 30 by ICP-MS, aqua regia digest		
Ground geophysics	Coverage			
Magnetic	Miihkali-Saramäki area			
EM	Saramäki	Data missing		
Kylylahti Copper/Altona				
Drillings	Total m			
11	1379	14 elements by ICP-OES	Au Pb fire assay, FAAS	

		188	188
MMI	52 samples	9 elements, analysis method unknown	
Geological Survey of Finland			
Aerogeophysics	1:100 000 map-sheet	Flown 1980, 200 m line spacing, 37 m altitude	
Mag			
EM			
Radiometry	U, Th, K		
Regional gravity	Coverage		
	200 km ²	4 points per km ² , survey year: 2000	
ZTEM flight	1250 line km	Line spacing 2,1 and 0.5 km	

*Major elements and a few trace-elements, **More recent XRF and a whole suite of trace-elements

Figure 14. Outokumpu Oy ground geophysical survey areas. Magnetic and slingram on the left, gravity on the right.

3.3. Geophysics and petrophysics

3.3.1. General petrophysical characteristics of VMS deposit

As the name suggests, volcanogenic massive sulfide (VMS) deposits typically contain massive to semi-massive sulfides, which mineralogy and degree of alteration significantly influence the petrophysical properties of the mineralization. VMS deposits typically occur in volcanic and volcanoclastic rocks, though they may also be hosted in sedimentary formations.

The characteristics of the deposit environment and the host rock, in turn, directly affect the contrast between the mineralized zones and the surrounding rocks, which subsequently influences the effectiveness of various geophysical methods used in exploration. Typically, the mineralized rocks in VMS deposits are very dense (approximately $>3500 \text{ kg/m}^3$) and conductive due to their high sulfide content. Magnetic susceptibility is variable depending on the presence of magnetite or pyrrhotite. Seismic velocities in massive sulfide zones are higher compared to surrounding rocks, but alteration zones may reduce velocities due to fracturing.

3.3.2. Petrophysics of Saramäki

Geophysics played a significant role in the discovery of the deposit in 1968. Following boulder indications, extensive exploration was conducted between 1959 and 1967, including geological mapping and geophysical surveys. Mineralization was discovered by drilling geophysical anomalies in 1968.

The petrophysics of the Outokumpu and Saramäki areas has been primarily derived from drill core samples. Ketola (1979) reported on the petrophysical properties of the Saramäki deposit and their influence on method selection. Leväniemi (2016) reported on the petrophysics of Saramäki as part of the Miihkali region. Ruotoistenmäki and Tervo (2006) reported on the geophysical characteristics of the entire Outokumpu area.

Outokumpu Oy drilled a total of 75 holes in the Saramäki area between 1967 and 1982. Petrophysical density and susceptibility measurements have been conducted on 18 of these cores, with a total of 4092 samples. An additional 5157 samples from 16 drill cored in the Miihkali area complement the dataset (see Figure 15). In later years other exploration companies have also conducted some petrophysical measurements during their investigations, but since these measurements have typically focused solely on rocks associated with the Outokumpu assemblage, their data does not provide a broader picture relevant to regional mineral exploration. Due to data ownership constraints and the limited scope of measurements by other companies, this DeepBEAT report focuses exclusively on data collected by Outokumpu Oy. The statistical classification of the dataset is based on lithological descriptions from drill logs and follows the classification used in the GEOMEX project (Table 5, Kontinen, 2006).

Figure 15. Locations of Outokumpu Oy’s drillholes containing petrophysics in Saramäki VMS deposit and Miihkali area.

For the selection of geophysical methods, it is important to determine the petrophysical contrasts between the mineralization, its host and country rocks, as well as their impact on the measurement results and interpretations. Figures 16–21 show the density and susceptibility distributions of the Miihkali region and the Saramäki deposit area in various ways. Median density and susceptibility values of mineralization, host and main country rocks in Miihkali region and Saramäki deposit area are presented in Table 6. Figure 22 and Table 7 briefly present the results of the petrophysical resistivity measurements.

Table 5. Rock classification and number of petrophysical samples from drill cores of Outokumpu Oy in Miihkali area. A total of 9217 samples, of which 4092 from Saramäki deposit area.

Group	Rock 1	Rock 2	N
Outokumpu assemblage	1 Outokumpu ultramafics and derived rocks	12 Serpentinite	1721
		16 Soapstone	192
		18 Carbonate rock	67
		19 Skarn	681
		110 Tremolitic skarn	448
		112 Diopsidic skarn	25
2 Outokumpu metabasites	24 Chlorite schist	306	
	21 Metabasite	395	
3 Outokumpu sulphides	33 Semimassive sulphides	36	
Schists after sedimentary rocks	5 Mica schists	51 Mica schists	4072
		57 Metasediment/Hydrothermal alt. mica schist	30
	6 Black schists	61 Black schists	492
		63 Calc-silicate rich black schist	74
Schists after volcanic rocks	15 Mafic volcanites	154 Amphibolite	9
	17 Felsic volcanites	171 Felsic metavolcanic rock	22
Plutonic rocks	24 Granitic plutonic rocks	247 Granitic pegmatite	2
Gneisses	35 Gneisses	353 Precarelian basement gneiss	23
	38 Granitic_granodioritic_gneisses_migmatites	381 Foliated granitic-granodioritic gneiss	181
Rocks of diverse, often more or less obscure origin	41 Quartz veins	411 Quartz vein	50
	42 Mylonitic_rocks	422 Mafic mylonite	9

Density

Based on the petrophysical dataset, the median density of the Saramäki mineralization (semi-massive sulfides) is 3430 kg/m³. The average density of other rocks of the Outokumpu assemblage within the deposit area is 2960 kg/m³, resulting in a density contrast of 470 kg/m³ between the mineralization and its host rocks. The median density of the surrounding mica schists is 2750 kg/m³, which means the density contrast, i.e. subtraction of mean values, between the host rocks (Outokumpu assemblage without sulfides) and the country rocks is 210 kg/m³. The density contrast between the mineralization and the country rocks is 680 kg/m³. Black schists, which in general are closely associated with Outokumpu-type mineralization (median density 2802 kg/m³), slightly reduce the overall density of the deposit package and its contrast to the surrounding mica schists. It is also noteworthy that the drill cores in the Saramäki deposit area do not contain strongly altered serpentinites, which elsewhere in the Miihkali area have a median density as low as 2550 kg/m³.

Susceptibility

The susceptibility values of rocks are often problematic to present statistically due to their dual-peak nature, which is why they are commonly shown as histograms. Susceptibility histograms of rocks in the Outokumpu region have previously been presented by Leväniemi (2016). In this study, however, median susceptibility values are presented for the simplification of the review. The highest ferromagnetic susceptibility values in the Saramäki deposit area are found in a few serpentinites (median $67\,000 \times 10^{-6}$ SI) due to their magnetite content, and in black schists due to their pyrrhotite content (median $14\,400 \times 10^{-6}$ SI). The rocks of the Outokumpu assemblage in Saramäki, including the mineralization, are generally weakly ferromagnetic, with median susceptibilities of $3,000\text{--}4,000 \times 10^{-6}$ SI. Some host rocks, such as soapstones, carbonate rocks, and certain skarn types, have quite low susceptibility values, below $1,000 \times 10^{-6}$ SI. The overall picture would be quite different if the host rocks in Saramäki contained more strongly magnetic serpentinites, which are commonly found in other Outokumpu-type mineralizations. The surrounding mica schists are paramagnetic and have low susceptibility values, with a median of approximately 300×10^{-6} SI.

Figure 16. Density-susceptibility diagram showing the distribution of median values of all rock types in Miihkali region including Saramäki deposit area.

Figure 17. Density-Susceptibility diagram showing the distribution of median values of different rock types in Saramäki deposit area.

Figure 18. Density box plots by rock types in Miihkali region showing median densities and their standard deviation as bar length. Number of samples written on the top of the bars. Rocks of Outokumpu assemblage are depicted by a red dot line.

Figure 19. Density box plots by rock type in Saramäki deposit area showing median densities and their standard deviation as bar length. Number of samples written on the top of the bars.

Figure 20. Susceptibility box plots by rock type in Miihkali region showing median susceptibilities and their standard deviation as bar length. Number of samples written on the top of the bars. Rocks of Outokumpu assemblage are depicted by a red dot line.

Figure 21. Susceptibility box plots by rock type in Saramäki deposit area showing median susceptibilities and their standard deviation as bar length. Number of samples written on the top of the bars. Rocks of Outokumpu assemblage are depicted by a red dot line.

Table 6. Median density (D) and susceptibility (K) values of mineralization, host and main country rocks in Miihkali region and Saramäki deposit area (N = number of samples).

Rock type	Miihkali region				Saramäki deposit area			
	N	Med D [kg/m ³]	N	Med K [10 ⁻⁶ SI]	N	Med D [kg/m ³]	N	Med K [10 ⁻⁶ SI]
Semimassive sulphides (mineralization)					36	3430	36	3070
Host rocks in Outokumpu assemblage package	4217	2764	4045	18 298	732	2960	667	3991
Country rocks, Mica schists	4102	2750	3418	278	2968	2750	2487	302
Country rocks, Black schists (strong association with mineralization)	566	2825	433	12 097	298	2802	249	14 365

Remanent magnetization

Lagacy petrophysical drillhole data from Saramäki does not contain measurement of remanent magnetization. However, previous studies have shown that the remanent magnetization of black schists in the Outokumpu region is generally significant and should be considered in magnetic modelling. In the Miihkali area, the Koenigsberger ratio in black schists has been reported to be as high as 10, indicating that remanent magnetization dominates over induced magnetization. The inclination of remanence has been reported as 45° and the declination as 90° (Leväniemi 2016; Ahokas 1984; Ketola 1979). The inclination of the current inducing field is approximately 75.5° and the declination 13.2°, so the estimated direction of remanence in black schists deviates significantly from the direction of the inducing field.

Resistivity

Although resistivity measurements from the Saramäki deposit drill cores have been reported (Ketola, 1979), only the resistivity data from drill hole JU-MI-80 (Fig. 11) still exists in digital form. This hole does not intersect the actual mineralization, but the Outokumpu assemblage with black schists has been intersected at depths of 463–494 m, 522–539 m, and 627–634 m (see Fig. 22). The measurement method and quality of the resistivity data are not documented, but the results indicate that the black schists are highly conductive compared to other rocks. In the Miihkali area, a few kilometers north of the Saramäki deposit, resistivity data is available from two other drill holes. Table 7 presents the median resistivity values for different rock types in the Miihkali area.

Polvijärvi / Saramäki

Drillhole; JU-MI-80

Figure 22. Petrophysical density, susceptibility and resistivity profiles in drillhole JU-MI-80 in Saramäki. Rocks of Outokumpu assemblage are show with grey polygon.

Table 7. Median values of petrophysical resistivities measured from drill cores in Miihkali region and Saramäki deposit area (Outokumpu Oy, a total of 3 drillhole in Miihkali region, 2150 samples of which 632 from the drillhole JU-MI-80 in Saramäki deposit area, see Fig. 11).

Group	Rock 1	Rock 2	Miihkali region		Saramäki JU-MI-80	
			N	Med Resistivity [Ω _m]	N	Med Resistivity [Ω _m]
Outokumpu assemblage	1 Outokumpu ultramafics and derived rocks	12 Serpentinite	751	80	-	
		16 Soapstone	90	10000	-	
		18 Carbonate rock	4	10000	1	7000
		19 Skarn	161	10000	-	
		110 Tremolitic skarn	48	850	19	900
		112 Diopsidic skarn	1	6000	1	6000
		113 Quartz rock	91	2000	2	5000
	2 Outokumpu metabasites	24 Chlorite schist	99	8000	14	4000
	21 Metabasite	7	8000	-		
Schists after sedimentary rocks	5 Mica schists	51 Mica schists	595	7000	545	8000
		57 Metasediment/Hydrothermal alt. mica schist	4	500	-	
	6 Black schists	61 Black schists	78	0	24	0.15
Schist after volcanic rocks	17 Felsic volcanic rocks	171 Felsic metavolcanic rock	22	8000	22	8000
Plutonic rocks	24 Granitic plutonic rocks	247 Granitic pegmatite	2	10000	-	
Gneisses	38 Granitic-granodioritic gneisses-migmatites	381 Foliated granitic-granodioritic gneiss	182	10000	-	
Rocks of diverse, often obscure origin	41 Quartz veins	411 Quartz vein	7	10000	4	10000
	42 Mylonitic rocks	422 Mafic mylonite	8	2500	-	

3.4. Geophysical proxies based on petrophysics and their implications for exploration

GRAVITY: Density contrasts between mineralization, host rocks, and country rocks suggest potential for gravity-based exploration. However, the small size of the mineralization precludes direct detection. The host rocks of the mineralization (Outokumpu assemblage + black schists) are approximately 200 kg/m³ denser than the country rocks and cause a small (~0.5 mGal) observable gravity anomaly at the surface outcrop, see the Figure 23. The 'host rock package' is only 20–70 meters wide and relatively horizontal in orientation. As it dips deeper to north-east at an angle of about 60 degrees, it soon disappears from view in gravity data. The package would be more easily detectable if it were vertically oriented.

Based on the petrophysical density data from Saramäki, gravity surveys can reveal the host rocks of the mineralization and indirectly help the exploration. On the other hand, it is noteworthy that the Saramäki area lacks serpentinites that are typically present in Outokumpu-type mineralizations. These serpentinites are significantly less dense and make it more difficult to detect horizontally oriented host rocks by lowering the average density of the host rock package.

Figure 23. Residual Bouguer anomaly as color surface and profile presentation. Mineralization subcrop and its horizontal cut offs at different depths and the geological vertical section interpreted from one of the drilling profiles (Kontinen et al., 2006) presented on the map plane.

MAGNETIC: The mineralization and the Outokumpu assemblage host rocks are weakly ferromagnetic, while the associated black schists are strongly magnetic compared to the paramagnetic mica schists that occur as country rocks. However, the black schists can contain very strong remanent magnetization, which affects the measurement results and complicates their

interpretation. At the surface outcrop of the deposit, the host rock package produces a variable magnetic anomaly, which also includes a negative response, presumably caused by remanent of the black schists (see Fig. 24).

Magnetic measurements, like gravity, can indirectly aid in locating mineralization by identifying host rocks. Notably, the Saramäki deposit does not contain the strongly magnetic serpentinites that are typically associated with other Outokumpu-type mineralizations. Their presence would produce a clearer response and bigger anomalies.

Figure 24. Magnetic vertical component as color surface. Mineralization subcrop and horizontal cut offs at different depths and the geological vertical section interpreted from one of the drilling profiles (Kontinen et al., 2006) are presented on the map plane. The subcrop is on the elevation level of ~185 m, ~5 meter below the thick (>5 m) moraine blanket.

RESISTIVITY/CONDUCTIVITY: The black schists associated with the deposit are highly conductive compared to all other rock types and are responsible for the anomalies observed in the Slingram (also known as Horizontal-Loop Electromagnetic Method) results. Although there is no petrophysical resistivity data available from the mineralization itself, it is presumably also conductive. The strong response from the black schists completely masks the response of the

mineralization, and due to the small size of the deposit, the sulfides cannot be detected separately in the measurements. The depth penetration of the legacy Slingram surveys conducted by Outokumpu Oy (with a coil spacing of 60 m) can be roughly estimated to be just 30–60 meters. Therefore, the host rock package, which dips steeply (~60°) to the northeast, can only be detected at its shallowest part (Figure 25).

The use of electromagnetic and electrical methods is justified due to the presence of strongly conductive black schists associated with the deposit, as well as the presumably conductive sulfide mineralization.

Figure 25. Slingram ($f=1775$ Hz, $a=60$ m) imaginary component as color surface. Mineralization subcrop with horizontal cuts of at different depths and the geological vertical section interpreted from one of the drilling profiles (Kontinen et al., 2006) are presented on the map plane. The subcrop is on the elevation level of ~185 m, ~5 meter below the thick (>5 m) till blanket.

3.4.1. Summary

Petrophysical data indicate that direct geophysical detection of the Saramäki mineralization is unlikely due to its limited size. However, gravity, magnetic, and electromagnetic methods can effectively identify host rocks, providing indirect exploration guidance. Petrophysical properties of the Saramäki VMS mineralization are consistent with the general characterization of VMS-

type deposits, although it also exhibits its own subtle and distinctive features due to the nature of the host and wall rocks at the deposit scale.

3.5. 3D model

3D modelling in the Saramäki area is based on the existing drillhole data such logged rock types and analyzed Cu, Zn, Co, and Ni grades. These were used to constrain the 3D model of the ore body seen in Figure 26. Observations of semi-brittle faults in drill core, together with interpreted faults from ground magnetic data were used to model the brittle structures (faults) possibly intercepting the mineralization at depth (Fig. 27).

Figure 26. Modelled mineralization (yellow body) with drill holes, digital elevation model (grey background) and scanned old Outokumpu Oy geological map.

Figure 27. Plan (left) and oblique views (right) of modelled brittle fractures/faults. Dark red faults represent faults modelled from drill core data and light blue and red lines represent faults interpreted from aeromagnetic maps.

3.6. Mineral system model for Saramäki Cu-Zn-Co-Ni deposit

There are several differences between more common type of VMS deposits (mafic-felsic hosted) and ultramafic-hosted Outokumpu-type deposits, considering their mineral system models. The overall system is similar with energy provided by subvolcanic intrusions and extension related faults acting as fluid pathways. However, the probable tectonic setting of Outokumpu-type deposits (OCT or OCC associated slow to ultra-slow spreading mid-ocean ridge) are generally relatively magma-poor, i.e., sub-volcanic intrusions are not as frequent or common (both spatially and temporally) as in other settings. Also, the hydrothermal fluid system can extend to a much greater depth, especially in OCC setting, as the detachment fault can extend up to 10 km below sea floor. As ultramafic-hosted deposits are not uncommon on the modern seafloor, it is evident that suitable and long-lived energy sources are present. Although serpentinization process is exothermic this is not enough to drive a high-T hydrothermal systems. Based on the abovementioned, we can assume that mafic (gabbroic) intrusion also drove the hydrothermal systems at the Outokumpu district, although mafic intrusive rocks occur only as minor dykes and small pods in the ophiolite fragments. However, the ultramafic formations are few kilometers wide, at largest, and perhaps 500–700 meters thick and thus represent thin slivers of the seafloor and mantle. Thus, the occurrence of any larger mafic intrusion would be very serendipitous.

For the fluid circulation system, we face the same problem as with other VMS deposits: it is very difficult to distinguish original faults related to extension from later fault zones formed

during subsequent deformation events. It is probably impossible to identify the original detachment faults or minor splay faults unless the alteration zones associated with Outokumpu deposits actually represent high-temperature hydrothermal alteration related to fluid flow along the detachment fault. Tremolite-chlorite-carbonate-quartz alteration in the detachment faults has been reported in several drilled ocean core complexes and is not dissimilar to alteration zones associated with Outokumpu-type deposits.

Because Outokumpu-type deposits are always associated with ultramafic-mafic ophiolite fragments dispersed within a relatively homogeneous metasedimentary belt, resulting in quite contrasting geochemical and geophysical properties, we can focus on the host rocks when creating proxies for the deposits. This is important because the deposits themselves may be too small, as in the case of Saramäki, to produce a sufficiently large geochemical or geophysical anomaly on their own.

Geochemical proxies

The host rocks and the sub-cropping mineralization should produce geochemical anomalies in till that are distinguishable from the compositional make-up of the surrounding mica schists, such as high MgO, Cr and Ni content of ultramafics, and directly ore related elements (Cu, Zn, Co, and Ni). Unfortunately, systematic gridded (or line) till sampling from the Saramäki area has not been done (or is missing). Also, Outokumpu Oy reports on till sampling done in 1970's indicate that surface till is not the best medium, as it probably represents long distance transported material. Also, surface geochemistry is of little importance for the proposed 3D prospectivity modelling.

Geophysical proxies

As discussed in the previous section, the mineralization-and especially the host rocks-also differ from the mica schist in several geophysical characteristics and can therefore be used as proxies. Perhaps the least useful is the conductivity data, as its the depth penetration is quite limited, particularly for the slingram method used in ground measurements. Magnetic measurements can “see” somewhat deeper as is evident in Figure 28. Further processing (inversion) can be used to model magnetics to several hundreds of meters (see Lahti et al. 2016 for previous modelling for Saramäki-Miihkali area). Gravity data can also be used, although the Outokumpu rock package at Saramäki is relatively thin and nor ideally oriented, however it lacks the highly serpentinized ultramafics present in large parts of the Miihkali massif which show as negative bouguer anomalies (less altered ultramafics do appear as positive bouguer anomalies). In Figure 28 the gravity anomaly created by the Outokumpu rocks can be seen to a depth of ca. 500 m. Again, 3D inversion can be used to model geology to even deeper levels. Description of the inversion techniques and results are beyond this report.

Summary

For 3D prospectivity mapping we are confined to using magnetic and gravimetric data and various derivatives and inversions. Drill data can be used for model validation (Outokumpu rocks present or absent).

Figure 28. Comparison of ground gravimetric and magnetic depth penetration. Arrows on the left indicate drill holes where Outokumpu rocks occur at ca. 500 m depth, while on the right the depth is only ca. 200 m.

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Annex A1: History of Changes of the document

Table 1: Table of document modifications.

Name	Affiliation	Function	Contribution / Review	Version
Tuomo Törmänen	GTK	WP2	Initial Version	1
Vesa Nykänen, Heikki Salmirinne	GTK	WP2	Review	1.1
Maarit Middleton	GTK	WP2	Review	1.2

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